

The Effect of Service Quality, Price Perception and School Image on WOM Intention Mediated by Satisfaction Variables at Yadika 4 Vocational School, Tangerang

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Abstract: This study aims to determine the Effect of Service Quality, Price Perception, and School Image on WOM Intention Mediated by Satisfaction Variables in YADIKA 4 Vocational School, Tangerang. The research design uses a quantitative approach and the type of research is causal research. The research method uses a survey. The research population of class X, XI, and XII students from SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang was 575 students. The sampling technique was proportional stratified random sampling with a total sample of 236 people. Collecting data in the form of a questionnaire. The research data were analyzed using the SEM method with data processing through the SmartPLS 3.0 application. The results showed that service quality, price, school image partially had a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction, and student satisfaction partially had a significant effect on WOM Intentions. School image is the variable that has the strongest influence on student satisfaction.

Keywords:- School Images, Satisfaction, Service, Price Perception, WOM Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the industrial revolution 4.0, the government seeks to improve the competitiveness of human resources and revitalize vocational education. The revitalization of vocational education is defined as preparing a workforce that is competitive, skilled, qualified, and relevant to the demands of the world of work. Seeing the phenomenon of SMK graduate students who have not been able to compete and not ready to work, the government through the Ministry of Education has tried to revitalize SMK. This strengthening is mainly in four vocational schools with expertise in agriculture, maritime, creative economy, and tourism. These four areas are being improved in quality to increase the Indonesian economy. This happens because SMK graduates are still not in tune with the needs of the world of work. According to data from the Ministry of Manpower and Transmigration (2010), only 30% of SMK graduates are accepted as employees in the formal sector and 70% work in the informal sector which have never been properly prepared by the SMK (Usman & Darmono, 2016, p. 13). Therefore, SMK must prepare their students become employees and entrepreneurs. According to Becker, SMK is an educational institution to produce specific human capital (Usman & Darmono, 2016, p. 13). When starting to study at SMK,

students are educated to commit to certain or specific skills that are directly related to certain business/industrial sectors.

One of the schools belonging to the Abdi Karya (Yadika) foundation which is the object of research is SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang. SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang is a favorite private school because it has been accredited A and is ranked 24th. Then, the connection between SMK Yadika 4, Tangerang and the freedom of learning that launched by the Ministry of Education and Culture, namely The Center for Excellence Vocational School Program which is the embodiment of President Joko Widodo's vision of improving vocational education as a strategy for developing Indonesian human resources (HR). The Center for Excellence Vocational School is a comprehensive breakthrough aimed at responding to challenges in the context of improving the current state of the Vocational High School to be more in line with the needs of the world of work. The Center for Excellence Vocational School program aims to produce graduates who are absorbed in the world of work or become entrepreneurs through in-depth and comprehensive alignment of vocational education with the world of work.

Service quality in the education sector has been the subject of numerous studies, given its ability to influence outcomes. Quality in education is a complex and multifaceted concept, and there is no single reliable definition of quality. As a result, there is no consensus on “the best way to define and measure service quality” (Annamdevula & Bellamkonda, 2016, p. 490). Previous research findings (Hwang & Choi, 2019, p. 7; Panda et al., 2019, p. 245; Saleem et al., 2017, p. 249) it was found that service quality had a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction. Then, (Osman & Saputra, 2018, p. 152) was found that service quality had a positive and significant effect on school image. Furthermore, previous research (Leonard, 2018, p. 46) was found that the costs incurred had a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction. Previous research (Liu & Lee, 2016, p. 47) found that price has a positive and significant effect on WOM. Previous research (Schlesinger et al., 2021, p. 11) found that satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on WOM. Previous research (Hwang & Choi, 2019, p. 7) was found that school image had a significant effect on student satisfaction. According to (Papadimitriou et al., 2018, p. 518) image has a positive and significant effect on WOM.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. WOM Intention

WOM intentions refers to how alumni anticipate making positive comments about their alma mater(Schlesinger et al., 2021, p. 4). WOM is an influential but rarely studied source of interpersonal communication in the field of marketing at the higher education level. Interest in doing positive WOM is related to one's attitude to get involved from favorable word of mouth with other consumers(van Tonder et al., 2018, p. 1351). According to (Jalilvand et al., 2017, p. 82)defines word of mouth as informal communication about products and services between those who consume these products or services and those who are interested in these products or services. This involves not only communication on the company's products or services but also on the company itself(van Tonder et al., 2018, p. 1352). Word of mouth can be positive or negative, and is received by potential customers before they experience the product or service(Shi et al., 2016, p. 394).

B. Student Satisfaction

Satisfaction is the result of service quality (Yusoff et al., 2015, p. 89). Linking service quality with student satisfaction indicates that the management of educational institutions should focus on the quality of services, information and facilities to increase student satisfaction and loyalty.The findings show that students' perceived quality is correlated with factors such as academic staff, study content, readiness for the labor market and acquired skills which consequently have an influence on students' loyalty to higher education institutions (Yusoff et al., 2015, p. 89).

C. Service Quality

Quality of service in education is a continuous process that is evolving all the time with opportunities in the hands of

the university for continuous improvement in service for the same customers (students), thereby giving service providers sufficient time to improve their level of service provision(Latif et al., 2019, p. 771). Higher education institutions have the opportunity to learn from their mistakes and exceed student expectations.

Service quality in education is perceived as a competitive aggregation between higher education institutions in terms of their dominance in creating unique learning experiences (Latif et al., 2019, p. 771). These experiences can be generated in a variety of ways: classroom teaching, extra-curricular activities, supervision, administrative support, or leadership.

D. Price Perception

Price is the value paid for a product as a form of the marketing exchange process. Many factors can affect the assessment of a value, including time constraints, price levels, perceived quality, and motivation to use available information about prices (Pride & Ferrell, 2016, p. 584).

E. School Image

In general, brand image plays a role in defining the product for consumers and distinguishing the company's offerings from competitors. One of the earliest definitions of brand image refers to the total impression that an entity makes on the minds of others (Dichter, 1985) in(Panda et al., 2019, p. 236). Brand image is the number of beliefs, attitudes, stereotypes, ideas, behaviors or relevant impressions that a person has about an object, person, or organization (Andreasen et al., 2008) in (Panda et al., 2019, p. 237). Brand image motivates consumers to buy a product or brand not only because of its functional attributes and consequences, but also because of the symbolic meaning associated with it.

III. FRAMEWORK

Based on theoretical studies and previous research, a framework of thought can be made as shown in Figure 1.

Picture 1: Framework

Based on Figure 1 framework, the research hypothesis are as follows:

- H1: Service quality has a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction
- H2: Price perception has a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction.
- H3: School image has a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction
- H4: Student satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on WOM Intention

IV. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Design

This research uses a quantitative approach with the type of causal research. According to Solomon et al. (2012, p. 113) causal research is a technique that attempts to understand causality. The independent variable as the causal factor and the dependent variable as the effect factor. The research population are students of Yadika 4 Vocational School, Tangerang, amounting to 575 students. Based on the calculation of the research sample using the Slovin’s formula (Nurdin & Hartati, 2019, p. 105) with an error rate of 5%, obtained a sample of 236 students. Sampling technique using proportionate stratified random sampling is a sampling technique used if the population has members that are not homogeneous and stratified proportionally (Hanief & Himawanto, 2017, p. 42).

B. Data Collection and Data Analysis

Data collection techniques through the distribution of questionnaires. The measurement scale used is a Likert scale with 5-point answer categories (Strongly Agree, Agree, Hesitate, Disagree, Strongly Disagree). Furthermore, the research variable WOM Intention is measured by three indicators (Papadimitriou et al., 2018, p. 515). Student Satisfaction is measured by five indicators (Panda et al., 2019, p. 243). Service quality is measured by nine indicators (Vázquez et al., 2015, p. 32); (Panda et al., 2019, p. 243). Prices or school fees are measured by three indicators (Sweeney et al., 2001, p. 212). Then, the school’s image is measured by two dimensions, namely tangibles has three indicators and intangibles has three indicators (Panda et al., 2019, p. 237), which can be seen in table 1.

The research data analysis technique uses quantitative data analysis with quantitative methods for hypothesis testing using the SEM method whose research data is processed through the SMARTPLS 3.0 application.

Variable	Dimension	Indicator	Measurement Scale
WOM Intention (bound variable/Z)		Say positive things about school to others. Recommend the school to others as a place to visit. Invite friends or relatives to register for the school.	Likert scale (ordinal data type)
Student Satisfaction (intervening/mediation/Y variable)		I did the right thing by enrolling in this school. My choice to enroll in this school was a wise choice. I found my experience with this school enjoyable. I am satisfied with my decision to study at this school. I think I did the right thing when I chose to study at this school.	Likert scale (ordinal data type)
Quality of service (Free Variable/X1)		My school has high quality resources and infrastructure. My school has good accreditation. My teacher does a quality job of teaching. The staff and management services at my school perform quality tasks. My school offers quality services compared to other schools. My school administration puts students' interests first. My school administration provides fast service. My school management is responsive to my needs. My school staff puts students' best interests first.	Likert scale (ordinal data type)
Price Perception (Free Variable/X2)		Affordable school entrance fees. Offers superior value that is worth the cost. Good service for the price.	Likert scale (ordinal data type)
School Image (Free Variable/X3)	Tangibles	School infrastructure Facility school location	Likert scale (ordinal data type)
	Intangible	I like school here. I am proud of this school. My school is a prestigious school	Likert scale (ordinal data type)

Table 1: Variable Operations

V. RESEARCH RESULT

Based on the findings of the research data in the table below, regarding gender, it can be clearly seen that the majority of respondents are male by 56.8% and female

respondents by 43.2%. From the description above, it shows that it turns out that the majority of respondents are male, which means that this vocational school is dominated by male students because students hope that after graduating from school they can immediately work.

Furthermore, regarding the current age of the respondents, it can be clearly seen that 39% of the respondents are 18 years old at most. Then, respondents aged 17 years amounted to 31.4%. Then, respondents aged 16 years by 26.3%, and those aged 15 years by 3.3%. From this description, it shows that in fact the majority of respondents are 18 years old and 17 years old because the

number of students is indeed more in class XI and XII so that the chances of becoming respondents are greater. In addition, students who in class XI and XII must have had experience while studying at SMK Yadika 4, Tangerang so that the assessment is more objective according to the experience that has been felt.

	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Man	134	56.8
	Woman	102	43.2
Respondent's Current Age	15 years	8	3.4
	16 years	62	26.3
	17 years	74	31.4
	18 years	92	39.0
	Class X	65	27.5
Currently Respondent is sitting in class	Class XI	72	30.5
	Class XII	99	41.9

Table 2: Characteristics of Respondents

Then, regarding the respondents currently sitting in class, the details of the research data are obtained as follows: it turns out that most of the respondents are in class XII by 41.9%. Meanwhile, respondents in class XI were 30.5%, and those in class X were 27.6%. From the description, it shows that in fact the majority of respondents are in class XII and XI because the number of students is greater so that they have a greater opportunity to become respondents. In addition, students who in class XI and XII will provide an assessment of the quality of their learning services which will be more appropriate because they already know the character of the teacher teaching and the experience felt.

The results of this data analysis from the statistical processing of SmartPLS 3. PLS-SEM is considered a variance-based approach to SEM to be appreciated for its ability to estimate both composites and factors (Akter et al., 2017, p. 1012).

There are two stages in processing SEM – PLS statistical data, namely testing the measurement model and testing the structural model.

A. First Stage: Measurement Model Test Results

The criteria that will be assessed in testing the measurement model are indicators of reliability/outer loading, internal consistency reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

a) Indicator Reliability or Outer Loading

Based on the findings of the research data in the table below, it can be clearly seen that the results of the validity test on the research variables obtained an outer loading value for each indicator greater than 0.70, meaning that the questionnaire statement item was declared valid.

The value of indicator loadings greater than 0.70 is declared valid because it indicates that the construct (variable) has been able to explain more than 50% of the indicator variances (Sarstedt et al., 2014, p. 108).

	School Image	Price Perception	Student Satisfaction	Service Quality	WOM Intention
SI1	0,767				
SI2	0,752				
SI3	0,716				
SI4	0,838				
SI5	0,770				
SI6	0,714				
PP1		0,780			
PP2		0,875			
PP3		0,854			
SQ1				0,789	
SQ2				0,735	
SQ3				0,712	
SQ4				0,766	
SQ5				0,780	
SQ6				0,826	
SQ7				0,792	
SQ8				0,756	
SQ9				0,707	
SS1			0,798		
SS2			0,797		
SS3			0,795		
SS4			0,857		
SS5			0,815		
WOM1					0,837
WOM2					0,889
WOM3					0,838

Table 3: Indicator Reliability / Outer Loading

b) Internal Consistency Reliability

Cronbach's alpha used to test the reliability of the study and the extent to which the indicators on the latent variable (construct) produce reliable convergent validity. According to (Garson, 2016, p. 64) recommend that the results of Cronbach's alpha 0.70 for an acceptable scale. Compared to Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability can lead to higher estimates of reliability. Specifically, the composite reliability value between 0.70 and 0.90 can be considered satisfactory (Garson, 2016, p. 63).

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
School Image	0,854	0,891
Price Perception	0,787	0,875
Student Satisfaction	0,871	0,907
Service Quality	0,910	0,926
WOM Intention	0,816	0,891

Table 4: Internal Consistency Reliability

Based on the findings of the research data in the table above, it can be clearly seen that the results of reliability testing on the research variables, which indicate that each research variable, whether using the Cronbach's alpha formula or composite reliability, produces a value for each variable above 0.70 which means that the questionnaire

research data is stated to be reliable or in other words the questionnaire statement used can measure the variables studied.

c) Convergent Validity

	AVE
School Image	0,579
Price Perception	0,701
Student Satisfaction	0,660
Service Quality	0,583
WOM Intention	0,731

Table 5: Convergent Validity

Based on the findings of the research data in the table above, it can be clearly seen that the results of the convergent validity test are that each research variable produces an AVE value greater than 0.5, meaning that the questionnaire statement items used can measure the variables studied so that the research data is declared valid.

An AVE value of 0.50 or higher indicates that on average, the construct explains more than half of the indicator variance. In contrast, an AVE value of less than 0.50 indicates that on average, more errors lag behind the items than the variance explained by the construct (Joseph F. Hair et al., 2014, p. 103).

d) Discriminant Validity

	School Image	Price Perception	Student Satisfaction	Service Quality	WOM Intention
School Image	0,761				
Price Perception	0,582	0,837			
Student Satisfaction	0,689	0,639	0,813		
Service Quality	0,603	0,596	0,651	0,763	
WOM Intention	0,568	0,417	0,540	0,589	0,855

Table 6: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Next, the calculation of cross loadings. Cross loadings are useful for assessing whether a construct has adequate discriminant validity, by comparing the correlation indicators of a construct with other constructs. A good model, produces a loading indicator value greater than 0.7 (some also uses a correlation value > 0.6) meaning that the research indicator is considered valid(Garson, 2016, p. 69).

	School Image	Price Perception	Student Satisfaction	Service Quality	WOM Intention
SI1	0,767	0,511	0,500	0,595	0,464
SI2	0,752	0,494	0,473	0,556	0,452
SI3	0,716	0,438	0,476	0,375	0,319
SI4	0,838	0,444	0,632	0,488	0,496
SI5	0,770	0,357	0,557	0,356	0,452
SI6	0,714	0,433	0,481	0,398	0,398
PP1	0,386	0,780	0,471	0,442	0,298
PP2	0,543	0,875	0,561	0,517	0,401
PP3	0,519	0,854	0,567	0,534	0,343
SQ1	0,503	0,422	0,469	0,789	0,482
SQ2	0,435	0,338	0,465	0,735	0,456
SQ3	0,459	0,332	0,479	0,712	0,446
SQ4	0,451	0,409	0,496	0,766	0,429
SQ5	0,407	0,380	0,450	0,780	0,494
SQ6	0,470	0,483	0,564	0,826	0,412
SQ7	0,469	0,568	0,547	0,792	0,486
SQ8	0,479	0,551	0,520	0,756	0,443
SQ9	0,471	0,589	0,458	0,707	0,406
SS1	0,609	0,504	0,798	0,454	0,377
SS2	0,570	0,562	0,797	0,452	0,387
SS3	0,527	0,472	0,795	0,525	0,388
SS4	0,527	0,503	0,857	0,558	0,428
SS5	0,565	0,549	0,815	0,633	0,580
WOM1	0,467	0,352	0,484	0,555	0,837
WOM2	0,489	0,317	0,452	0,455	0,889
WOM3	0,503	0,400	0,445	0,485	0,838

Table 7: Cross Loading

Based on the results of the research data findings in the table above, it can be clearly seen that the results of the cross loading, which turned out to be each indicator item on the research variables produced a value greater than the cross loading value on the right and left sides so that it can be said that the research data is valid.

Although predominantly using cross-loadings and Fornell-Larcker criteria to estimate discriminant validity, recent investigations found that these two criteria are not reliable as a detector of discriminant validity problems

(Geebren et al., 2021, p. 7). To solve this problem of insufficient discriminant validity detection, Geebren suggested a new approach to assess discriminant validity namely the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) of correlation. “(HTMT) is the mean of all cross-indicator correlations of constructs measuring different constructs [...] relative to the (geometric) mean of the mean correlations of indicators measuring the same construct”. The acceptable threshold of the HTMT test is 0.9 which is recommended(Geebren et al., 2021, p. 7).

	School Image	Price Perception	Student Satisfaction	Service Quality	WOM Intention
School Image					
Price Perception	0,710				
Student Satisfaction	0,792	0,767			
Service Quality	0,688	0,698	0,721		
WOM Intention	0,678	0,518	0,629	0,683	

Table 8: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Based on the findings of the research data in the table above, the results of the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) can be clearly seen that the correlation value for each variable is still below the threshold of 0.9 as recommended (Geebren et al., 2021, p. 7). This means that the research data is declared valid.

After the testing phase of the measurement model is declared to have met the requirements because it has produced valid and reliable data, it can be continued with structural model testing.

B. Second Stage: Structural Model Test Results

The criteria assessed in the structural model testing include: Collinearity, Predictive Relevance (coefficient of determination), Goodness of Fit Model Test, Effect Size (f square), Cross-validated redundancy (Q2), and Path coefficients and Significance (P values).

a) Collinearity

Based on the research findings in the table bellow, it can be clearly seen that the results of the collinearity test are that each VIF value is less than 5, which means that none of the research data has multicollinearity. The threshold for collinearity is values 1 – 5. If the VIF value exceeds 5, it is indicated that there is collinearity between research indicators (Sarstedt et al., 2014, p. 9).

	VIF		VIF		VIF
SI1	2,512	SQ1	2,618	SS1	2,071
SI2	2,452	SQ2	2,373	SS2	2,114
SI3	1,557	SQ3	1,957	SS3	2,034
SI4	2,250	SQ4	2,333	SS4	2,632
SI5	1,849	SQ5	2,424	SS5	1,978
SI6	1,629	SQ6	2,682	WOM1	1,666
PP1	1,483	SQ7	3,144	WOM2	2,242
PP2	1,903	SQ8	2,537	WOM3	1,837
PP3	1,740	SQ9	2,011		

Table 9: Collinearity

b) Predictive Relevance or coefficient of determination (R2)

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Student Satisfaction	0,600	0,595
WOM Intention	0,291	0,288

Table 10: Coefficient of determination (R2)

Based on the research findings in the table above, the percentage of student satisfaction after being influenced by service quality, price, school image, obtained R square is 0.600 or 60% ((R²) > 0.75 including the category of moderate influence) and the remaining 40% is determined by factors other factors not studied. Then the percentage of WOM Intention after being influenced by student satisfaction obtained R square is 0.291 ((R²) > 0.25 including the category of weak influence) or 29.1% and the remaining 70.9% is determined by other factors not examined.

c) Test Goodness of Fit Model

This study uses the Goodness-of-Fit (GoF) index to measure the fit of the model. Goodness of Fit (GoF) is measured using the geometric mean of the average communality score (AVE values) with an average value of R2 (which can be seen in the endogenous construct) and can be calculated using the following formula, (GoF = √(AVE × R2)) (Farooq et al., 2018, p. 177). Cut off values for Goodness of Fit (GoF): GoF_{small} = 0.1; GoF_{medium} = 0.25; GoF_{large} = 0.36. According to Henseler et al. (2016) in (Farooq et al., 2018, p. 177), good model fit indicates that the model is parsimony and makes sense.

The tested model has a GoF value of 0.625, meaning that the research model is declared to have good fitness as shown in the table below

Construct	AVE	R2	Result
School Image	0,579		
Price Perception	0,701		
Service Quality	0,583		
Student Satisfaction	0,660	0,600	
WOM Intention	0,731		
Average scores	0,651		
AVE*R2	0,391		
GoF = $\sqrt{(AVE \times R2)}$	0,625		very good

Table 11: Goodness of Fit Model

From the GoF calculation above, the GoF result is 0.625. From these results it can be concluded that the performance between the measurement model and the structural model can be said to be fit (GoFlarge) because it meets the standards above 0.36 including the strong category.

d) Test Effect Size (f square)

The results of R square (R^2) will change if one of the exogenous constructs (independent variable) is removed from the research model, then to evaluate whether the omitted exogenous construct can have an important impact on endogenous constructs (dependent variable) it can be seen from the effect size (f^2) results. The guideline for assessing effect size f^2 is that values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35, respectively, represent small, medium, and large effects (Cohen, 1988) (Hair Jr et al., 2017, p. 211).

	School Image	Price Perception	Service Quality	Student Satisfaction	WOM Intention
School Image				0,197	
Price Perception				0,096	
Service Quality				0,099	
Student Satisfaction					0,411
WOM Intention					

Table 12: Effect Size (f square)

Based on the findings of the research data in the table above, it is clear that the effect size (fsquare) are as follows:

- The magnitude of the influence of school image on student satisfaction obtained f-square value is 0.197 which is in the interval range between 0.15 - 0.35 including the category of moderate influence.
- The magnitude of the effect of price on student satisfaction obtained f-square value is 0.096 which is in the interval range between 0.02 – 0.15 including the category of small/weak effect.
- The magnitude of the effect of service quality on student satisfaction is obtained by the f-square value of 0.099 which is in the interval range between 0.02 – 0.15 including the category of small/weak influence.

- The magnitude of the influence of student satisfaction on WOM intention to obtain f-square is 0.411, which is above 0.35, including the category of strong influence.

e) Cross-validated redundancy(Q2)

Cross-validated redundancy (Q^2) used to determine the extent to which the independent variables in this research model have relevance to predict the dependent variable. The value of Q^2 is above zero ($Q^2 > 0$) which implies that the structural model has a high predictive ability (Hair et al., 2019, p. 19). The results of the cross-validated redundancy (Q^2) 0.02, 0.15, 0.35 for weak, moderate, strong degree of predictive relevance.

	SSO	SSE	Q2(=1-SSE/SSO)
School Image	1416.0000	1416.0000	
Price Perception	708.0000	708.0000	
Service Quality	2124.0000	2124.0000	
Student Satisfaction	1180.0000	726.7861	0,3841
WOM Intention	708.0000	561.7751	0,2065

Table 13: Cross-validated redundancy (Q2)

Based on the findings of the research data in the table above, regarding Cross-validated redundancy, it can be clearly seen as follows:

- It turns out that the variables of service quality, price, school image as antecedent variables are able to predict student satisfaction variables, the value (Q2) is 0.3841,

including the category of strong influence because it is greater than 0.35.

- Furthermore, the student satisfaction variable was assessed as being able to predict the WOM intention variable, the value (Q2) was 0.2065 including the category of moderate

influence because it was in the interval range between 0.15 – 0.35.

f) Path coefficients and Significance (P value)

This hypothesis testing is used to answer the hypotheses that have been formulated previously and at the same time answer the research objectives. Researchers tested the significance of the hypothesis using the Bootstrap

procedure in SmartPLS with 5000 sub-samples(Sarstedt et al., 2014). The critical values for the two-tailed test were 1.65 (Sig. 0.1), 1.96 (Sig. 0.05), and 2.58 (Sig. 0.01). The strength and significance of the path coefficients were evaluated for the hypothesized structural paths between the constructs.

Hypothesis	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics	P Values	Hypothesis	Result
Service Quality → Student Satisfaction	0,2692	0,2674	0,0652	4.1298	0.0000	H1	Accepted
Price Perception → Student Satisfaction	0,2604	0,2525	0,0822	3.1702	0.0016	H2	Accepted
School Image → Student Satisfaction	0,3749	0,3864	0,0739	5.0719	0.0000	H3	Accepted
Student Satisfaction → WOM Intention	0,5395	0,5431	0,0597	9.0308	0.0000	H4	Accepted

Table 14: Hypothesis Testing Results

Based on the findings of the research data in the table above, the results of this research hypothesis testing are as follows:

- The results of the partial test show that the quality of service has a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction, this is evidenced by the acquisition of the calculated T value of 4.1298 and Sig. 0.000. Due to the P values (0.000) < 0.05 and < 0.01, it means that there is a significant effect, thus H1 is accepted. Furthermore, to determine the magnitude of the effect of service quality on student satisfaction, the path coefficient (β) is 0.2692 including the category of strong influence because it is above 0.25 as recommended by (Keith, 2015, p. 62).
- The results of the partial test show that the price has a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction, this is evidenced by the acquisition of the calculated T value of 3.1702 and Sig. 0.0016. Due to the P values (0.0016) < 0.05 and < 0.01, it means that there is a significant effect, thus H2 is accepted. Furthermore, to determine the magnitude of the effect of price on student satisfaction, the path coefficient (β) is 0.2604 including the category of strong influence because it is above 0.25 as recommended by (Keith, 2015, p. 62).
- The results of the partial test show that the school's image has a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction, this is evidenced by the acquisition of the calculated T value of 5.0719 and Sig. 0.0000. Due to the P values (0.000) < 0.05 and < 0.01, it means that there is a significant effect, thus H3 is accepted. Furthermore, to determine the magnitude of the influence of school image on student satisfaction, the path coefficient (β) is 0.3749 including the category of strong influence because it is above 0.25 as recommended by (Keith, 2015, p. 62).
- The results of the partial test show that student satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on WOM intention, this is evidenced by the acquisition of the calculated T value of 9.0308 and Sig. 0.0000. Due to the P values (0.000) < 0.05 and < 0.01, it means that there is a significant effect, thus H4 is accepted. Furthermore, to determine the magnitude of the effect of student satisfaction on WOM intention, the path coefficient (β) is 0.5395 including the category of strong influence because it is above 0.25 as recommended by (Keith, 2015, p. 62).

VI. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the findings of research data and quantitative data analysis, the results of the research discussion can be described as follows:

- The results of the partial test show that the quality of service has a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction, this is evidenced by the acquisition of the calculated T value of 4.1298 and Sig. 0.000. Due to the P values (0.000) < 0.05 and < 0.01, it means that there is a significant effect, thus H1 is accepted.

Meanwhile, the magnitude of the effect of service quality on student satisfaction obtained by the path coefficient (β) is 0.2692 including the category of strong influence. This means that the more the quality of service is improved, the more student satisfaction will increase. Quality of service in education is an ongoing process that evolves over time to make continuous improvements for students, thereby giving service providers sufficient time to improve their level of service provision (Latif et al., 2019, p. 771).

As for the quality of service that can increase student satisfaction, it can be seen from the outerloading value of the highest service quality, which is 0.826 regarding school administration employees prioritizing the interests of their students. Meanwhile, on student satisfaction, the highest outerloading value was 0.857 regarding respondents being satisfied with the decision they made to study at this school. This means that employees who work in the administration of the school show work behavior that prioritizes the needs of their students so that students feel satisfied with the services provided by administrative employees, such as there are students who need a letter for internship/field work practice, so a letter of assignment is immediately made. Then the administrative staff records student data correctly and accurately, such as late coming to school or absenteeism. Furthermore, the recording of school fee data is recorded neatly and stored properly so that nothing is missed so that students feel satisfied.

Then, the lowest outerloading result of service quality is 0.707 regarding school staff prioritizing the best interests of students. Meanwhile, on student satisfaction,

the lowest outerloading was 0.795 regarding respondents who felt that the respondent's experience with this school was pleasant. This means that in terms of service quality, it turns out that there are still school staff who do not prioritize the best interests of students so that it has an impact on decreasing student satisfaction. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the quality of services, especially staff who work in schools to be willing to help all student needs as long as it supports teaching and learning activities so that students have a pleasant experience and a sense of satisfaction arises.

Based on the research findings above, it shows that there are still deficiencies in service quality. This means schools need to analyze the quality of the services they provide in order to function efficiently and effectively in a highly competitive environment (Santos et al., 2020, p. 4). In addition, schools should strive to determine strategies that are oriented towards meeting all student needs.

The findings of this study have relevance to previous research (Hwang & Choi, 2019, p. 7); (Saleem et al., 2017, p. 249) it was found that service quality had a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction.

- The results of the partial test show that the price has a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction, this is evidenced by the acquisition of the calculated T value of 3.1702 and Sig. 0.0016. Due to the P values (0.0016) < 0.05 and < 0.01, it means that there is a significant effect, thus H2 is accepted.

Meanwhile, the magnitude of the effect of price on student satisfaction obtained by the path coefficient (β) is 0.2604 including the category of strong influence. This means that the more affordable the price / school fees, the more satisfied students will be.

The price or school fees that have an impact on student satisfaction can be seen from the outerloading value at an affordable price/cost, the highest is 0.875 regarding offering an advantage value that is comparable to the cost. Meanwhile, on student satisfaction, the highest outerloading value was 0.857 regarding respondents being satisfied with the decision they made to study at this school. This means that affordable school fees make students feel happy because the costs that have been incurred by the parents of these students have obtained superior values that are comparable to costs such as a good teaching system, teaching discipline, extracurricular activities, and other forms of learning activities so that students feel satisfied studying at the Yadika 4 Vocational School, Tangerang.

Then, the result of the lowest outerloading of the price or school fees is 0.780 regarding affordable school entrance fees. Meanwhile, on student satisfaction, the lowest outerloading was 0.795 regarding respondents who felt that the respondent's experience with this school was pleasant. This means that for students, the school fees are still quite expensive, even though the parents of the students are still able to pay the tuition fees. Students hope that this school fee can be reduced so that students are

happy because they pay affordable school fees with good teaching quality.

Based on the research findings, it can be seen that the price or school fees perceived by students are still quite expensive so that it has an impact on the level of satisfaction. If the price paid is not commensurate with the educational services provided, a sense of dissatisfaction will arise. Therefore, the price as a determinant of the purchase of services by spending money (Saleem et al., 2017, p. 241). Zeithaml (1988, p. 241) states that price in the context of consumer perception as giving up something to achieve a certain service. Price can be defined as a concept of quality and satisfaction in the context of service. Customer satisfaction can be determined through the perceived price. The factors used to identify prices are reported by many researchers. The perceived value of students can be checked with the help of various factors like, tuition fees, cost of books and training materials. If students are satisfied with the service or product they receive in return for what they have paid, then they consider the product to be a quality product and feel satisfied.

The findings of this study have relevance to previous research (Leonnard, 2018, p. 46) that was found that the costs incurred had a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction. Ledden et al (2011, p. 1245) was found that the lower the school fees, the higher the student satisfaction.

- The results of the partial test show that the school's image has a positive and significant effect on student satisfaction, this is evidenced by the acquisition of the calculated T value of 5.0719 and Sig. 0.0000. Due to the P values (0.000) < 0.05 and < 0.01, it means that there is a significant effect, thus H3 is accepted.

Meanwhile, the magnitude of the influence of school image on student satisfaction obtained by the path coefficient (β) is 0.3749 including the category of strong influence. This means that the more the image of the school is improved, the more student satisfaction will increase. The main strategy for high school is to control the competitive environment by creating a different brand image for the school itself. A unique brand image can positively affect their reputation which can have a major influence on students' experiences at school (Panda et al., 2019, p. 234).

The school image that can increase student satisfaction can be seen from the outerloading value on the school image, which is 0.838 regarding respondents who are happy to go to school here. Meanwhile, on student satisfaction, the highest outerloading value was 0.857 regarding respondents being satisfied with the decision they made to study at this school. This means that the image of the school that is formed in students' perceptions is a positive image, so students feel happy to be able to go to school at Yadika 4 Vocational School, Tangerang. Respondents are happy to go to school at Yadika 4 Vocational School because the teaching system is fun, the

teacher shows a willingness to help students who have difficulty in learning and provide teaching until the students understand and understand, then the school facilities are also considered to support learning activities so that students decide to study at SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang. Students feel satisfaction from attending SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang because what they want is as expected. Based on the results of the research findings indicate that a good school image leads to satisfaction. If a high school presents a good image to its students, then these students will have a high level of satisfaction and build positive behavioral intentions (high retention and positive recommendations about the school to others). Therefore, the image of an educational institution can be recognized as a term that is equivalent to service quality (Hwang & Choi, 2019, p. 4).

Then, the lowest outerloading result of school image is 0.714 regarding the respondent's school is a prestigious school. Meanwhile, on student satisfaction, the lowest outerloading was 0.795 regarding respondents who felt that the respondent's experience with this school was pleasant. This means that there is still a slightly less good assessment regarding the image of the school, especially the Yadika 4 Tangerang Vocational School, which cannot be said to be a prestigious school for its status as a private school because there are still better private schools with more expensive costs. The impact of the image of Yadika 4 Tangerang Vocational School, which is considered not to be considered a prestigious school, does not reduce satisfaction too high.

The findings of this study have relevance to previous research (Hwang & Choi, 2019, p. 7) it was found that school image had a significant effect on student satisfaction. Osman & Saputra (2018, p. 152) were found that the university's brand image had a significant effect on satisfaction.

- The results of the partial test show that student satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on WOM intention, this is evidenced by the acquisition of the calculated T value of 9.0308 and Sig. 0.0000. Due to the P values (0.000) < 0.05 and < 0.01, it means that there is a significant effect, thus H4 is accepted.

Meanwhile, the magnitude of the effect of student satisfaction on WOM intention obtained by the path coefficient (β) is 0.5395 including the category of strong influence. This means that the more student satisfaction increases, the more word of mouth (wom) intention will increase.

The student satisfaction that can increase word of mouth (wom) intention can be seen from the outerloading value on student satisfaction which is 0.815 regarding respondents who think that respondents do the right thing when respondents choose to study at this school. Meanwhile, in word of mouth (wom) intention, the highest outerloading value was 0.889 regarding recommending the school to others as a place to visit. This means that students who feel satisfaction from attending SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang show their interest in recommending to

others because the choice of students at SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang is considered correct and as expected so they feel satisfied. Therefore, students are willing to recommend to others who are still having difficulty in determining which private schools are considered good. From the results of the research findings above, it shows that students feel satisfaction so they intend to do word of mouth to other parties. Student satisfaction is "the extent to which the institution's service performance meets student needs" (Saleem et al., 2017, p. 239). Student satisfaction is influenced by student expectations and student perceptions of the services and quality of services provided. Student satisfaction with school has institutional, individual, and social welfare. According to institutional arguments, satisfied students are much more likely to persist in their studies and succeed academically. Student satisfaction can be easily achieved with outstanding service standards.

Then, the lowest outerloading result of student satisfaction is 0.795 regarding respondents who feel that the respondent's experience with this school is pleasant. Meanwhile, in word of mouth (WOM) intention, the lowest outerloading was 0.837 regarding saying positive things about school to others. This means that students are not fully satisfied with Yadika 4 Tangerang Vocational School because sometimes there are services that have not been fulfilled properly so students feel disappointed. However, students will also convey the advantages and disadvantages of SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang to other people who ask about this SMK Yadika 4 school.

The findings of this study have relevance to previous research Previous research (Schlesinger et al., 2021, p. 11) found that satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on WOM. Jiewanto et al (2012, p. 21) found that student satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on WOM Intention.

VII. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of hypothesis testing and research discussion, the findings of this study can be concluded as follows:

- School image partially has the strongest and most significant effect on student satisfaction. This means that the more the image of the school is improved, the more satisfaction of the students of SMK Yadika 4, Tangerang.
- Service quality partially has a strong and significant effect on student satisfaction. This means that the more the quality of service is improved, the greater the satisfaction of students at SMK Yadika 4, Tangerang.
- Price partially has a strong and significant effect on student satisfaction. This means that the more affordable the price, the higher the student satisfaction of SMK Yadika 4, Tangerang.
- Partial student satisfaction has a strong and significant effect on women's intention. This means that the more student satisfaction increases, the more women's intention for SMK Yadika 4, Tangerang will increase.

VIII. SUGGESTION

A. Academic Advice (Theoretical)

- Further researchers can add variables of trust in schools, and behavior of interest in enrolling in schools so that they are expected to produce comprehensive research findings.
- Based on the research findings of the inner model test, the research findings indicate a strong influence. So for further researchers, they can also conduct research in educational institutions such as educational course institutions or at universities to find out the results of the comparison.
- The research methodology can use mixed methods of analysis in the form of interviews and questionnaires.

B. Practical Advice

Based on the findings of the pre-survey that the author has done, it turns out that there are still shortcomings. So the authors can provide research suggestions as follows:

- In the service quality variable, the highest outerloading value was obtained by the school administration employee prioritizing the interests of his students. It is recommended that teachers and the school foundation of SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang continue to maintain and improve administrative staff who are professional at work in order to increase student satisfaction in receiving quality services.
- In the price perception variable (school fees), the highest outerloading value is obtained, which is to offer an advantage that is proportional to the cost. It is recommended that teachers and school foundations at SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang maintain a more affordable price or school fees balanced by excellent service quality so that the level of student satisfaction increases.
- In the school image variable, the highest outerloading value is obtained, the respondents are happy to go to school here. It is better if the image of the school continues to be maintained and improved in terms of providing learning services and facilities for supporting learning activities so that students feel happy to study at SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang and feel satisfied.
- In the student satisfaction variable, the highest outerloading value obtained is that the respondent thinks the respondent is doing the right thing when the respondent chooses to study at this school. It is recommended that teachers and the foundation of SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang continue to maintain and improve the quality of learning services, provide affordable prices or school fees, and maintain the image of the school so that more students are willing to recommend SMK Yadika 4 Tangerang to other parties.

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